

The Portrayal of Women as a MARRIONETE in Henry Ibsen's a Doll's House

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M.Banupriya

Assistant Professor in English

Pavai Arts and Science College for Women

Abstract

Henrik Johan Ibsen was born in 1828 in the town of Skien on the Southeast coast of Norway. At the age of fifteen Ibsen decided to become a professional artist and in 1884 he was apprenticed to an apothecary in Grimstad. Ibsen, the father of modern drama, began his career by writing romantic history plays. In 1870s he turned to social and ethical concerns. This was the play made Ibsen internationally famous. Ibsen was the first major dramatist to write tragedy about ordinary people in ordinary situations, using colloquial prose for dialogues. A Doll's House is a realistic play. It is an anti-romantic play both in its theme and setting. The play deals with the problem of man – women relationship through the mirror of marriage. The theme of the play is the assertion of wife's rights. Nora Helmer, remains the puppet and doll wife of her husband. She remains passive and self-effacing for eight years. At the end, she asserts herself and becomes an individual in her own right.

Keywords: apothecary, ethical, puppet, doll.

A Doll's House the most famous and best known of Ibsen's plays was published in 1879. The play was a crushing indictment of contemporary middle-class marriage. It created immediate sensation. It was this play that made Ibsen internationally famous. Ibsen was the first major dramatist to write tragedy about ordinary people in ordinary situations, using colloquial prose for dialogues. A Doll's House is a realistic play. It is an anti-romantic play both in its theme and setting. The play deals with the problem of man-woman relationship through the mirror of marriage. The theme of the play is the assertion of wife's rights. Nora Helmer, remains passive and self-effacing for eight years. At the end, she asserts herself and becomes an individual in her own right.

Nora and Torvald Helmer seem to lead a happy life with three beautiful children. Torvald is fond of his pretty young wife. But he treats her as his pet and possession. He wants her to play the role of a beautiful, careless, happy wife. He controls everything in the house including the eating habits of Nora. He gives her money for buying fine clothes and let her dress and dance at the fancy dress ball in the apartment of the Stenborgs the night after Christmas. He does all these to stimulate his sexual desires. Nora is her husband's doll and the children are her doll.

Torvald is dead against borrowing and sees to it that the home is run within his income. He falls seriously ill, in order to save his life Nora takes him to a warm country in Italy by borrowing money from Krogstad, by forging her father's signature in the bond, without her husband's knowledge. When Torvald decides to dismiss Krogstad from the Bank, Krogstad threatens Nora that he will expose her forgery if her husband does not retain him in the Bank. But Torvald dismisses Krogstad, who writes a letter to him exposing Nora's forgery. Nora thinks that her husband would take all the blame on himself, when he comes to know the truth. In order to prevent that she even thinks of committing suicide. But all her hopes are shattered when her husband revealed his true colour. Then she realises that she has so long lived with a stranger and decides to break all marital ties with him. So she walks out of his house, slamming the door and goes out in quest of her identity.

Nora recalls her past when she was with her father at their home, she could not have any personal opinion on anything. Her father never allowed her to differ from him. Her father called her his "doll child" even when she had become old enough to marry, and played with her just as she played with her dolls when she was young. Nora was confined in her father's home and did what he wanted. She had never left home. After that she was simply transferred from her father's hands to that of Torvald's. Then it was Torvald who arranged everything to his taste.

In Torvald's home she is treated as a child. She is protected, petted, patted, dressed up, given pocket money but is not allowed to be herself. She has not been allowed to be her true self either by her father or by Torvald, her husband. As both have treated her like a doll, she has to play the "doll" throughout. She plays the doll with her husband and pleases him and helps him to keep his image as the head of the house.

The doll-world set up makes Nora nurture romantic notions about her husband's love for her. She hopes that when her husband comes to know about the forgery committed by her, through Krogstad's letter, he would perform a miracle and would take up all the blame on him and let Krogstad publish his letter. Torvald shatters all her hopes by showing out his true colour and Nora understands that all her romantic notions are illusions of her doll-world. Nora, the heroine of the play, is modern in the sense that she readily gives up her traditional role of the doll wife and doll-mother in order to get self-liberation individuality and independence. In its middle-class setting, its plot and its medium, the play tends to be modern.